

OER – Intro Statistics Courses

Kim Massaro

University of Texas at San Antonio, One UTSA Circle, San Antonio, TX 78249

Abstract

Open Education Resources (OER) aim to provide students a low-cost option for required materials in a course. Considering the increasing financial burden on students attending University, the introduction of a low-cost option could be the key that keeps more students enrolled each semester. Various methods of OER have been utilized for Basic Statistics at UTSA, an introductory statistics course, to include the use of an Open Stax textbook, the creation of interactive presentations, videos, and notes. These resources have been created by the instructor using online tools such as Camtasia, Panopto, and Playposit. The resources are then available to students throughout the duration of the course, and thereafter if they choose to download and save them. The aim is to provide students with enough *free* supplementary information on the topics in the course, that a standard textbook is not necessary to succeed. This paper discusses OER materials utilized in the course and the effect that OER has on students taking introductory statistics courses. In addition, providing assessment data comparing student performance between OER and non-OER sections of the same course at UTSA.

Key Words: Open Education Resources, OER

1. Introduction to OER

What is OER? OER is open education resources, or open-sourced resources. These are teaching materials in the public domain that can be used freely, without charge to both instructors and students. These resources can include, but are not limited to, lesson plans, quizzes, exams, instructional models, simulations, and more. OER is becoming more and more widely used to help alleviate students' financial burden because they provide either free or low cost required course materials. In addition to helping students, it also allows instructors freedom to create their own materials tailored specifically to their course.

1.1 Adopting OER

Open Education Resources have been adopted in an asynchronous online section of STA 1053, Basic Statistics; a course that is part of the core curriculum at the University of Texas at San Antonio (UTSA). Basic Statistics is one of the courses listed for students to take to satisfy their Mathematics component which focuses on quantitative literacy in logic, patterns, and relationships involved in the understanding of key mathematical concepts and the application of appropriate quantitative tools in everyday experience (1).

1.1.1 Basic Statistics Course

Basic Statistics is a 16-week semester long course taken by a wide variety of majors across the University. The course is broken down into five units throughout the semester:

Unit 1: Descriptive Statistics
Introduction to Statistics
Numerical Summaries

Graphical Representations

Unit 2: Probability

Probability

Probability Distributions (Binomial and Normal Probability Distributions)

Unit 3: One-sample Inference

Confidence Intervals for one-sample means and proportions

Hypothesis Tests for one-sample means and proportions

Unit 4: Hypothesis Tests

Two-Sample Hypothesis Test for Independent Samples

Matched Pairs Test

Chi-Square Tests

Unit 5: ANOVA and Regression

Analysis of Variance

Simple Linear Regression

1.2 OER Survey

A survey was given to two sections of Basic Statistics in the Spring of 2022 to gather student demographics in the course and assess their knowledge, opinions, and feedback about Open Education Resources. The survey was administered during the first two weeks of the semester through the Learning Management System, Blackboard Learn. The survey consisted of 36 questions, adapted from a survey given by Allan Hancock College (2). The survey was analyzed according to three components: Demographic and Educational Questions, Expenses for Courses, and Reducing Costs, for a sample of $n = 339$ students. To begin the survey, students were asked if they had ever taken a course at UTSA that used open educational resources instead of purchasing a textbook. 50% of students in the sample responded, "I'm not sure." This means that students may have little knowledge about open education resources and/or aren't aware of when a course offers sections with this option in place to reduce the cost of textbooks.

1.2.1 Summary of Survey Data on Expenses

Students were asked: How much out of pocket costs did your course materials cost you this semester? According to the results, students answered:

$\leq \$100$	$= 15\%$
$\$101 - \200	$= 23\%$
$\$201 - \300	$= 28\%$
$\$301 - \400	$= 19\%$
$\$401 - \500	$= 10\%$
$> \$500$	$= 5\%$

In response to a series of questions about the cost of textbooks:

66% of students did not purchase the required course materials, 41% of students did not register for a certain course due to the cost of required course materials, 50% of students chose to take one section of a course over another, 43% of students took fewer courses during the semester, 22% of students dropped or withdrew from a course because they couldn't afford the required textbooks, and 20% of students performed poorly in the course because they could not afford to purchase the textbook.

1.2.2 Summary of Survey Data on Reducing Costs

There are many resources outside of campus in which students can obtain the required course materials. In an attempt to see which resources students used to try and lower costs of the required materials, a series of questions were asked about their purchasing methods. 20% of students avoid

purchasing the textbook all together. 15% of students purchase textbooks from external sites (other than the campus bookstore). 36% of students rent digital or printed textbooks from the campus bookstore. 5% of students use a reserved copy of the textbook from the library. 21% of students purchase used copies of the textbook from outside sources. Students were then asked how helpful the promise of a zero-textbook cost degree would be for them. 30% of students said that it would help them finish their degree in less time, while 32% of students said it would make a big difference in whether they are able to complete their degree at all.

So, exactly how much money is OER saving students in Basic Statistics at UTSA? The required purchased textbook cost \$182.95 in previous semesters, while the low-cost OER adoption of the course costs students \$37.95. Therefore, students are saving \$145 by taking a section of Basic Statistics that has adopted the use of OER.

2. OER in Basic Statistics

The asynchronous online section of Basic Statistics that adopted the use of low-cost Open Education Resources is split into the five units listed in Section 1.1.1. Each of these units are made up of module components. Each unit has two modules which includes a Read, Watch, and Practice section. Followed by a module homework, then subsequently a Unit exam after two modules have been completed.

2.1 Read/Watch/Practice

The Read section of each module is a powerpoint presentation with lecture slides. The Watch section of each module is a lecture video that accompanies the Read section in which students are asked to watch the video and take notes filling in the associated lecture outline as they go. The practice component consists of two-four shorter videos. Each video has a document with an example problem attached. The students are asked to print the document or copy the problem on their paper and work through the solution to the example problem while watching the video. In this way, students are learning by doing. All documents, presentations, and videos have been created by the instructor of the course therefore allowing the customizability of creating course materials specific to the content covered and tailored directly for students at this level. With content creation, a lot of time and effort is spent on creating the materials to make them accessible along with continuously updating them from semester to semester. Online technology is constantly changing with more and more tools available to increase the ability of student engagement.

2.2 Assessments

Each learning module is followed by a set of questions in the form of a Homework assignment. Homework assignments utilize the online homework platform, WebAssign by Cengage. This is reason for the low-cost OER based course, instead of free. Students are charged the open-sourced version of using Cengage's WebAssign, a single term fee. Each homework consists of a series of 10-15 questions. Every student is given the same set of questions, but all data is randomized, therefore no two students will have the same dataset. There are Unit Exams assigned after the material is completed for two learning modules. Exams are assigned through the WebAssign platform. Students are given one day to complete the exam, however it is a timed exam. Therefore, students must still study for an online exam and know how to perform the questions similar to that of which they saw on the homework assignments. Table 1 describes the lecture materials developed in the course along with the assessments given throughout the semester. PlayPosit is a tool that has been used to develop a series of questions throughout the lecture videos. The video will pause and a question will be asked. The student has numerous attempts to answer the question, giving them an opportunity to re-play the video to locate the answer. These videos act as a way to collect attendance credit even though it is an online class to encourage students to participate in the lecture material. As the lecture material is the most important component of the course when a purchased textbook is not required, it is essential that students utilize the information given in the videos to learn and practice.

Table 1: OER Materials in Basic Statistics

Item	Tool	Number Created	Required?	Percent of Grade?
Presentation Slides	Powerpoint	23	No	0%
Lecture Videos	PlayPosit	23	Yes	5%
Example Problems	Camtasia	31	No	0%
Homework	WebAssign	12	Yes	30%
Projects	WebAssign	6	Yes	15%
Exams	WebAssign	5	Yes	50%

3. Analysis of Student Data

3.1 Exam Results

The question then becomes, are students able to succeed in a Basic Statistics course that offers OER? An analysis was conducted comparing two non-OER sections of Basic Statistics in Spring 2021 to two OER sections of Basic Statistics in Spring 2022. A two-sample t-test was conducted for each of the Unit Exams in order to examine if significance differences existed between the average exam scores of the two courses.

Table 2: Analysis of Exam Scores

Exam	Sample Size Sp2021	Sample Size Sp2022	Average Sp2021	Average Sp2022	t Stat	P-value	Conclusion
1	292	322	82.46	85.34	-3.066	0.0023	Significant Difference at 5%
2	296	328	70.68	73.6	-1.925	0.0547	No Significant Difference
3	285	328	72.88	75.42	-1.451	0.1474	No Significant Difference
4	285	313	71.27	75.51	-3.053	0.0024	Significant Difference at 5%
5	272	311	80.27	83.16	-2.032	0.0426	Significant Difference at 5%

From the results of the analysis, Exams 2 and 3 showed no significant difference. The topics from Exams 2 and 3 correspond to Units 2 and 3. While Exams 1, 4, and 5 showed a significant difference at the 5% level. However, by taking a closer look at the exam averages themselves; the average exam scores for all exams is higher in Spring 2022 than in Spring 2021. Spring 2022 were the sections that had adopted the use of OER materials. Therefore, the instructor-based content creation appears to have a better approach in helping students succeed than the purchased textbook option in previous semesters.

3.2 Overall Student Performance Results

Furthermore, additional comparisons were completed in an effort to explain how student performance varies from non-OER sections to OER based sections of Basic Statistics. Table 3 summarizes the grade distribution for two asynchronous online sections of Basic Statistics that are non-OER, while Table 4 summarizes the grade distribution for two asynchronous online sections of Basic Statistics that are OER based. For purposes of this analysis, the plus/minus grading scale was not used.

Table 3: Spring 2021 (Non-OER)

Letter Grade	Number of Students	Percent of Students
A	118	37%
B	82	26%
C	53	17%
D	22	7%
F	32	10%
Drops/Withdraws	9	3%
TOTAL	316	100%

Table 4: Spring 2022 (OER)

Letter Grade	Number of Students	Percent of Students
A	148	42%
B	92	26%
C	51	14%
D	20	6%
F	33	9%
Drops/Withdraws	12	3%
TOTAL	356	100%

The results of the grade distributions for comparing across sections of non-OER vs OER based Basic Statistics are further shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Comparing Non-OER to OER Basic Statistics Courses

3.3 Next Steps

While a low-cost option does help students financially, a no-cost option would be even more beneficial. Pressbooks is an open book creation platform that instructors can create, adapt, and share accessible, interactive, web-first books (3). It gives the instructor the freedom to piece together open-sourced information and customize a textbook specifically for their course. Pressbooks will continue to be an option moving forward in Basic Statistics as the instructor works on creating a version to meet the needs of the learning outcomes in the course. Videos will continue to be updated on a semester basis as new technology becomes available and more current real-world examples can be applied. Documents will continuously be adapted to increase the accessibility of the entire online asynchronous course. LMS based assignments will be created to get rid of the low-cost of utilizing WebAssign so that all required materials for the course will be free to the student and present a no-cost option in the future.

References

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